

~ FIP mini-questionnaire ~

Build your FAIR Implementation Profile

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SSHOC-NL-SEH - SSHOC-NL Socio Economic History

Community description	
Name of Community	ODISSEI
Description of Community	ODISSEI
Supporting Links	http://odissei-data.nl/
Research Domain	Social Sciences, Social and Behavioural Science
Data Steward	
Date of FIP creation	May 2025

FAIR principle	Question	FAIR enabling resource types	FERs (2023)	FERs (2025)
F1	What globally unique, persistent, resolvable identifiers do you use for metadata records?	Identifier service	DOI, Handle, ORCID	DOI, Handle, ORCID
F1	What globally unique, persistent, resolvable identifiers do you use for datasets?	Identifier service	DOI(to use), Handle	DOI (F), Handle
F2	Which metadata schemas do you use for findability?	Metadata schema	MARC21, EAD3, DDI, DCAT2	MARC21, EAD3, DDI, DCAT2
F3	What is the schema that links the persistent identifiers of your data to the metadata description?	Metadata-Data linking mechanism	DOI, Handle	DOI, Handle
F4	Which service do you use to publish your metadata records?	Registry	Dataverse, NDE	IISG Dataverse (to be discontinued), NDE Dateregister, DataverseNL (Future)
F4	Which service do you use to publish your datasets?	Registry	Dataverse, DANS SSH data station (future)	IISG Dataverse (to be discontinued), DataverseNL(F), DANS SSH data station (F), EASY (in the past)
A1.1	Which standardized communication protocol do you use for metadata records?	Communication protocol	OAI-PMH, HTTPS, REST API	OAI-PMH, HTTPS, REST API
A1.1	Which standardized communication protocol do you use for datasets?	Communication protocol	REST API, HTTPS, OAI-PMH	REST API, HTTPS, OAI-PMH
A1.2	Which authentication & authorisation service do you use for metadata records?	Authentication & authorisation service	HTTPS	HTTPS
A1.2	Which authentication & authorisation service do you use for datasets?	Authentication & authorisation service	SWORD; CLARIN AAI	SWORD; CLARIN AAI
A2	What metadata preservation policy do you use?	Metadata preservation policy	RDA CTS RDA Core Trust Seal Certification	None
I1	What knowledge representation language (allowing machine interoperation) do you use for metadata records?	Knowledge representation language	RDF (OWL, RDFS)	RDF (OWL, RDFS), SKOS
I1	What knowledge representation language (allowing machine interoperation) do you use for datasets?	Knowledge representation language	XML, HTML, RDF (RDFS, OWL),	XML, HTML, RDF (RDFS, OWL),
I2	Which structured vocabularies do you use to annotate your metadata records?	Structured vocabularies	EAD, DCAT, MARC21	EAD, DCAT
I2	Which structured vocabularies do you use to encode your datasets?	Structured vocabularies	HISCO, AMCO, Historical ICD (H-ICD), IDS	HISCO, AMCO, Historical ICD (H-ICD), IDS, HISCLASS, OCCSCORE, PRESGL, SEI, NPBOSS
I3	What semantic model do you use for your metadata records?	Semantic model	IDS	IDS, PICO, schema.org (F), PROV-O (F)
I3	What semantic model do you use for your datasets?	Semantic model	SHACL (future)	SHACL (F), BIO (F)
R1.1	Which usage license do you use for your metadata records?	Usage license		
R1.1	Which usage license do you use for your datasets?	Usage license	CC-BY-SA, CC-BY-NC	CC-BY-NC, CC BY-SA 4.0
R1.2	What metadata schema do you use for describing the provenance of your metadata records?	Provenance model	DCAT	DCAT, PROV-O (F)
R1.2	What metadata schema do you use for describing the provenance of your datasets?	Provenance model	DCAT	DCAT

Link to this document: <https://bit.ly/yourFIP>